

A STUDY OVER TO PRODUCTIVITY AFFECT OF STRESS STRUCTURE OF TAX OFFICERS

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***Abstract:** Stress is existing in every moment of human life and affects people in various ways. Daily stress can manifest in every moment of life individuals are helpless in the face of different events and different solutions people are pushing edging. This situation affects the quality of life of the people. Individuals at home, at work, at short due to problems they encounter in daily life is exposed to stress. In this case against the individuals' home, family, business, job-related issues falling to worry about fulfilling responsibilities. In business stress affects the performance and efficiency of the individuals' work. One of the many sources of stress acting on the individual's performance varies according to the source of the stress reactions of individuals. If organizational structure employees in a positive direction if we can talk about positive stress but effective, otherwise this is not even in question. Another aspect of the individual's own shopping in the case of reverse psychology with the drop in the working environment, negative stress is raised hoist power and individual causes a negative reflection on the performance of shopping. The aim of this study is between stress and stress sources of public employees and is to the effects of the performance of employees.*

***Keywords:** Stress, Stress sources, public employees, performance*

Although the many changes taking place in the world where people are always exposed to the concept of stress is never changed. Human encounters with stress in many states and conditions. One of these cases is the stress experienced by individuals working in a business environment. An individual working day, a large part of his time in the business environment where most exposed to workplace stress is being spent on. People have characteristics they are effective in creating organizational

stress factors and stress for many reasons. Working life can be considered from two perspectives, including the private sector and the public sector in terms of people. A general view that was more stressful to have a busy schedule due to the private sector. But the public sector also has at least as much as the private sector in stress situations. Forming properties due to stress, it carries many units in the public sector has a structure. One of these units is also Finance Organization performing work related

duties. Tax officials stress that one of the employees of this institution is located in the most public employees living in group. Because the tax officers on duty to supervise the fulfillment of the obligations of taxpayers Individuals who live an intense job stress. In addition, tax collectors, and they did not carry the financial responsibility for the collection of money from taxpayers. Thus the formation of stress takes place in a natural way. therefore, stress that what they are doing with tax officials are also affected. Tax officers can experience loss of productivity due to stress. Interruption of work, which means pressure on employees' productivity leads to increased loss of taxpayers. said the study „The Impact of Tax Officers Efficiency of Buildings A Study on Stress” is. Descriptive study was prepared by the method. said the study „The Impact of Tax Officers Efficiency of Buildings A Study on Stress” is. Descriptive study was prepared by the method. said the study „The Impact of Tax Officers Efficiency of Buildings A Study on Stress” is. Descriptive study was prepared by the method.

1. Stress Concept

Many people's physical or emotional event, their response to the situation and circumstances are expressed as stress. Hans Selye, they gave no significant response in cases where people have been identified as stress¹. Many different result² The notion that

¹ ÖZKALP AnwarandKırel Çiğdem, Organizational Behavior, (Eskişehir, Ankara University Open

stress can create positive or negative effects³. But is that the general perception of the negative effects of the stress. Failure can occur if the opinion is advocated that the positive results of the stress and obtain successful results. Stress the positive impact of the efficiency of employees in the presence of a disciplined management approach exemplified in the business environment to increase.

1.1. Stress in the Business Life

Stress is a condition where people live every moment. Business life is another stress environment in which people live. Because people spend a significant portion of the business environment in days. different views in the literature on stress in the workplace are available. McGrath⁴ organizational stress factors that occur in the business environment has stated as follows:

- Task-related stress,
- Role-related stress,
- Behavioral stress resulting from environment,
- Stress caused by the physical environment,

Education Publications: 2003), pp. 187-190. (Eskişehir, Ankara University Open Education Publications: 2003)

² Acar Baltas and Zuhul Baltaş, Stress and Coping Strategies, Remzi Bookstore, 14.Bas I, Istanbul, 1995, s. 73-74

³ Sit down, Perseverance. And Stress Management in Business: Respect Effect on Performance Analysis. Efficiency Magazine. Say: 1994/4, ss. 113-128

⁴ McGrath, JE (1976), Stress And Behavior In Organizations, in mddunet (Ed), Handbook Of Industrial And Organizational psychology Chicago

- The stress arising from the social environment,
- Individual self-caused stress.

In another opinion Luthans⁵ organizational stress factors that occur in the business environment has announced four titles.

- Organizational policies,
- Structural characteristics of the organization,
- Physical conditions
- Organizational processes

Eroğlu explaining the organizational stress factors⁶ The formed six domains:

- General causes of stress,
- Physical environmental conditions,
- Economic conditions, social life,
- Work life
- Personality structure.

Aydın⁷ organizational causes of stress:

- Why stress caused by organizational policy,
- Organizational structure resulting stress causes,
- The causes of stress caused by physical conditions in the business environment,
- Job-related stress causes the structure
- The organization has summarized the causes of stress caused by interpersonal relationships.

⁵ Luthans, Fred (1992), Organizational Behavior. McGraw-Hill Inc., New York pp. 403-412 Six Edition

⁶ Eroğlu F., 1998, Behavioral Sciences, Beta Publishing, Istanbul ss. 310-326.

⁷ Aydın, Sule, 2004, „Organizational Stress Management”, Journal of Dokuz Eylül University Institute of Social Sciences, Vol. 6, Issue. 3

The most important stress factor of a person's working life and the job itself. Because of the intensity of work, work-related problems, work on their psychological functioning of the individual and the fatigue is one of the main reasons that may cause exposure to stress. In addition, the individual's own characteristics are influenced by stress. The capabilities of the individual, personal boundaries, it is influenced by the formation of stress and they can not do. Owned by individuals may also affect the efficiency of stress. Usually losses adversely affected the efficiency may be encountered. But the reverse situation can also occur. Increasing stress on an individual's job motivation stemming from the work itself can also lead to efficiency gains.

2. Results

2.1. Problem of Research

Stress affects people who have everything in your life in any way. Because in effect starting from the periphery and the man himself and reveals a response. People live their working life the impact and consequences of stress. Labor productivity is the most important concept of life is also affected by stress. This is how it is affected by the stress of productivity in research and the impact of general business and private life stress will be explained how it is.

2.2. Methods and Models of Research

Research is prepared according to General Scanning model. Description method is used. Defining a situation without

changing the existing method based on the description of the General Scanning model has an approach aimed at⁸ events or circumstances are telling the scan pattern as observe. That is a scientific depiction⁹ It is made.

2.3. The Relationship between Stress Structure and Productivity of Tax Officers

Many of those involved in the public sector tax officers¹⁰. It represents a moiety. Each employee productivity in business life as affected by many factors, tax collectors is exposed to stress factors. business itself is the cause of stress for an individual is influenced by a lot of positive or negative result. But the job is not alone cause stress. The imbalance in the distribution of work in the work environment, job satisfaction of employees, wage imbalance and stress are among the factors constituting several reasons. This is the primary factor in terms of running costs of the factors. It is willing to be satisfied with the fees charged by individual employees. Fees received from individuals¹¹ Because

satisfaction is least expected it difficult to be happy about efficiency.

Tax officers is another stress factor becomes dull and monotonous work for working in the public sector. Because individuals in the monotony of work that occurs because a certain intimidation pace, it makes weariness occur. This situation leads to individual undergoes stress.

Organizational stress factors that are important in our age and mobbing is a factor arising¹² (Bullying, psychological pressure) remains valid for tax officials. Tax officers mobbing¹³ factors they are exposed to in terms of organizational management style. Management felt the pressure too much tax officers are exposed to stress. Even in this case up to insult it is supported by statements in an advanced stage. Therefore, loss of productivity in employees is made. Mobbing¹⁴ not only does not lead to loss of productivity. mobbing that may cause the employee to leave work.¹⁵ It may cause individuals to suffer the psychological and physical disease. Business¹⁶ employees

⁸ Karasar, N.(1984). **Bilimsel Araştırma Metodu**. Ankara: Hacetepe Taş Kitapçılık, s. 74

⁹ Yıldırım C.(1966). **Eğitimde Araştırma Metotları**. Ankara: Akyıldız Matbası

¹⁰ Gülümser KESKİN. Örgütsel Stres ve Erzurum da Kamu Çalışanları Üzerine Bir Uygulama. Verimlilik Dergisi. Say: 1997/2, ss. 141-164

¹¹ YAMUÇ(2014) V.A., Kadın Ve Erkek Çalışanların Stresle Baş Etme Sürecinde Yönetimden Beklentilerine İlişkin Nitel Bir Araştırma, Eskişehir Osmangazi Üniversitesi İlib Dergisi, Nisan 2014, 9(1), 21-40

¹²http://www.canaktan.org/yonetim/psikoloji-k-siddet/genel-olarak.htm#_edn5.Access.03.09.2015

¹³ Sahin, O, Salmanlı, E. (2015), Made In mobbing Employees On The Concept And Work Stress Study, The Journal of Academic Social Science, vol. 20, 355-368

¹⁴<http://www.leymann.se/english/12100e.htm>. Access.03.09.2015

¹⁵ Sahin, O, Salmanlı, E. (2015), Made On The Concept And Employees Work Stress Study of mobbing, The Journal of Academic Social Science, vol. 20, 355-368

¹⁶<http://www.ceis.org.tr/dergidocs/makale23.pdf>. Access.03.10.2015

exposed to stress in your life, there are some expectations in this life. expectations of employees can also turn to the reasons which lead to stress. The work is the first to work an employee expectations fee. If the individual is not satisfied with the wages of unhappy individuals can be exposed to stress. The result is composed inefficiency. One of the expectations is the job satisfaction of employees¹⁷. The satisfaction of the individual's work directly affects productivity. An employee who is happy on the job, an employee doing their job fondly one can strive to be more productive and hardworking. But otherwise, it is not unlikely to expect from the individual. In terms of job satisfaction of employees subject to tax officers and taxpayers are getting into too much administration. Because of an employee who loves his work so as to cover this aspect of business administration, attitudes and behaviors of taxpayers against those who are among the most important factors affecting job satisfaction. happy to be in the business of tax officials, therefore exposure to stress directly affects productivity. reduce employee productivity hinder this case the taxpayers get the service that is expected from officers and administration officials also expect from the work efficiency.

Another factor affecting the stress of running a workload distribution. Staff

¹⁷ AKGÜNDÜZ Sevgül, „Job Satisfaction of employees of the Organizational Sources of Stress and Its Impact on Bank Employees Made For A Survey”, Dokuz Eylül University Institute of Social Sciences, Unpublished Master Thesis, İzmir, 2006

members include workload will increase the workload on some individuals not distributed in a fair way. Increased workload will lead to more fatigue of individuals. It will also lead to psychologically wear. Because individuals are exposed to stress due to overwork. the productivity is lost due to the stress in individuals. In individuals with less workload it is composed of different results. a monotone and monotonous work life for the individual's job is made less. This situation is caused by the employee's monotonous. bored in the business environment shows early states such as suffocation. Also in this case it consists of stress. Thus, loss of productivity as a result consists in this case. One example of this situation in terms of tax officials are the timeout period. Some of the employees during this period occurred in the last months of the calendar year consists in an excessive workload. In this case the more usual workload, which causes stress levels of employees to attract more. Thus, the decline in the efficiency of tax officials is composed¹⁸.

Factors affecting organizational stress and the stress levels of employees in the public sector is different organizational structures can vary. A hospital worker with a public security officer of stress factors and levels are not the same. Hence the stress factors can vary according to tax officials and other public employees.

¹⁸ Tolga Erdoğan, A. Sinan Ünsar, Necdet Süt, Stresin Çalışanlar Üzerindeki Etkileri: Bir Araştırma, Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi İktisadi Ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi Y.2009, C.14, S.2 S.447-461.

The assessment of the tax officers by the managers is one of the stress factors that put pressure on the employees. When executives decided to favor one side in an unfair situation it arises officers. Thus, a group consists wronged. With this positive decision in favor of conflict between groups may occur. Conflict is increasing the stress level on both sides. increasing tax officials stressed structure leads to loss of productivity. Conflict environment may be a factor that increases productivity in some cases. It may lead to increase the number of work done by creating competition among tax officials. Therefore, productivity is increased naturally.

Many features can influence the stress of the employees of the public sector. Often designated for the emergence of tax officials, administrators unfair evaluations, uncertainty in the job description are some of these features. Because many of these and it is affected by tax officials stress factors at the organizational level. Organization is reflected again from stress-induced negative impact on the organization. Because the factors that cause stress destroys the efficiency of tax officials. Hence they also maintain a negative impact on organizational reasons.

Individual properties owned by tax officials also are important factors affecting stress. The individual's age, sex, features such as character among the reasons that lead to stress. Being old tax officer can lead to negative consequences in some ways. slow due to this reason the remaining employees in the use of technology in particular exposed

to stress and fertility is decreasing. But it can improve the efficiency of experienced owned by the same employees. Young is young individuals tax officers who are weak in terms of technology yaşanmazken experience problems due to a problem in use may be susceptible to stress and loss of productivity will suffer from this angle viable.

Exposure to stress can vary due to the gender of the tax officials. Men working in a unit where a female employee may not work comfortably outnumber workers, among others. Feel comfortable that the tax officer can become stressed. Thus it may experience loss of productivity. In addition, the character of the female employees¹⁹ as the cause to remain weak in dealing with the stress of having an emotional structure. The result also experienced the loss of efficiency. Male employees are considered to be more successful when in a stressful situation that mainly act more logic in this regard. In this respect can not lose efficiency.

3. Conclusion

Stress is a phenomenon that exists in human life. One of the areas where most intense is the work environment. Because individuals spend most of the time in a work environment in their daily lives. Stress also has implications for the productivity of individuals in the work environment. This effect is the cause of many influences

¹⁹ Nergüz Bozkurt, Stres, „Öğretmen Stresi ve Stresle Başa Çıkma Yöntemleri”, Kişisel Gelişimde Çağdaş Yönelimler Sempozyumu, 27-28 Nisan 2004 Ankara, s.142

positively or negatively affect stress²⁰ it can be effected. Learn stress-free life can not be considered positive or negative results must be capable of learning how to manage stress. This should be done both in the individual sense of organizational sense. Because the subject of our study is „to employee productivity within an organization stress“ due to the influence of both the employee and the stress mention should be made aware of the organization. In addition, while both of these should be done in parallel with each other. So be positive results. Individuals coping with stress and those proposed to be done to manage stress: Recreation and motivation, fitness and balanced nutrition, training and development, self-knowledge and understanding thereof. Organization of coping with stress and those proposed to be done to manage stress: Stress management training, time management, socialsupport.

²⁰ Robert H. Rosenand Lisa Berger. The Healthy Company: Eight Strategies to Develop People, Productivity and Profits. New York: Jeremy P. Teacher/Perigee Books, 1991,s. 9; Tim Hindle. Reducing Stress. London: Dorling Kindersley, 1998, s.10.

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